

Research and Innovation Indicator Framework – An example from the Danish CoARA chapter

Research Intelligence Network Netherlands
Poul Meier Melchiorson, 23 June 2026

Background, Motivation, and Action

December 3rd, 2021, the Ministry of Higher Education and Science closed the national research indicator. All national monitoring closed as well.

No current suggestions for a new national research indicator

The board at Aalborg University: a need for a new indicator to maintain positive effects of the old research indicator: increase in the total *number of publications*, increase in publications in journals with *high impacts*, and more *citations*.

Opportunity to learn from some of the challenges in the old system

The Strategic Council for Research and Innovation at AAU appointed **a committee with representatives** from the four faculties, administrative staff from the innovation, finance, and research analysis teams, and an external consultant from NIFU, Oslo.

Indicator design was carried out between September - December 2022

The Committee involved in creating the AAU Research Indicator

September – December 2022:

- Developing the indicator

Fall 2022- Spring 2023:

- Hearing processes in the Academic Councils and HSU

June 2023:

- Approved by the AAU board

Fall 2023:

- Implementation

Fall 2025

- Innovation added to data catalogue

- **Jakob Stoustrup**, Chair, Professor, Technical Faculty of IT and Design
- **Winnie Jensen**, Professor, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences
- **Torsten Nygård Kristensen**, Professor, Faculty of Engineering and Science
- **Birger Larsen**, Professor, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
- **Tommy Nielsen**, Senior consultant and representative of the Finance and Accounts Department
- **Christian Müller**, Specialist coordinator and representative of the Finance and Accounts Department
- **Jørgen Albretsen**, Academic officer and representative of AAU Innovation
- **Poul Meier Melchiorsen**, Chief Consultant and representative of the VBN Team
- **Kathrine Bjerg Bennike**, Senior Consultant and representative of the VBN Team
- **Gunnar Sivertsen** (external consultant) Professor at the Nordic Institute for Studies in Innovation, Research and Education (Oslo)

Aim of a New Research Indicator

SHOW DIVERSITY IN
RESEARCH AS WELL AS
EXCELLENCE

BE INTERNATIONALLY
RECOGNIZABLE

ACCOUNT FOR
DIFFERENCES
BETWEEN DISCIPLINES

APPLY RESPONSIBLE
METHODS AND
METRICS

SHOW IMPACT

BE PART OF THE AAU
BUDGET MODEL

From an EU
perspective, there is a
large push to
incorporate Open
Science in the
development of new
metrics and research
assessments

Inspiration from
International
research evaluation
agreements –
*Agreement on
Reforming Research
Assessment (ARRA)*
&
*the San Francisco
Declaration on
Research
Assessment (DORA)*

*“Research assessment practices should induce a research culture that recognises **collaboration, openness, and engagement with society**, and that provides opportunities for multiple talents” (ARRA 2022, 12)*

*“[...] the need to eliminate the use of **journal-based metrics**, such as Journal Impact Factors, in funding, appointment, and promotion considerations;*

*the need to assess research on **its own merits** rather than on the basis of the journal in which the research is published [...]” (DORA 2012)*

AAU Research and Innovation Indicator

Innovation broadens the range of merit

AAU Research and Innovation Indicator

Conclusion:

Part A = subject neutral and applied directly to support internal distribution of basic research funding

Part B = developed to showcase subject specific research strategies at the department level

Scientific Publishing (part A)

We use bibliometrics because:

- New research is expected to manifest itself through publications/patens
- The impact of the research is later expected to be expressed through citations

We calculate a combined point for publications and citations with a complicated, but transparent equation because:

- We have scientific evidence that this equation creates comparability across different research fields' publication and citation practices

Simple message for the individual researcher:

Make research that is worth publishing in a good journal, that can be used in other contexts, and which will be cited

Basic points for publication types (part A)

Publication types	Points
Journal article, Conference article in journal, Letter, Review, Contribution to book, Contribution to report, Conference article in proceeding	1
Book, Report, Doctoral thesis	5
Encyclopaedia article, Anthology, Editorial, Case Report, Preprint*	0,5
Patent	2

*Monitor the development

Norwegian register for scientific journals, series and publishers

Why:

1. In a research climate with changing publication practices including open access and new business models, predatory journals have become an increasing problem.
2. An authoritative list, like the Norwegian list, ensures that researchers review and evaluate the relevance and legitimacy of a journal and not the publishers.

HOW:

1. Choose a publication channel, which you believe best suits your research scope.
2. Check if the publication channel is on the list. Use the following link: <https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/>
3. If the publication channel is *not* on the list, you have the possibility to suggest a new journal, book series, or publisher. This is done through a standardized form found via the link above.
4. If you publish in a journal or a book series, check if the channel is indexed in the citation database Scopus.

Calculation of Points (part A)

Publications indexed in Scopus are weighted with a citation metric. Publications, which are not indexed in Scopus, have the weight 1 (world average)

Citation weighted publication point:
 $P * W_{impact}$

$$W_{impact} = SC * FWCI + (1 - SC) * 1.0$$

P are the "raw" publication numbers, SC is the department's coverage in Scopus, and $FWCI$ is the "Field Weighted Citation Impact" calculated in SciVal

Conclusion:

For departments with a high coverage in Scopus, citations will carry much weight. Contrary, for departments with a low coverage, citations will carry less weight

Examples on calculation of points

$$\text{Citation weighted publication points} = P * SC * FWCI + (P - (P * SC))$$

*Example with a FWCI **over** the world average (i.e. over 1)*

In this case, the department will receive more publication points 124 publication points
 $100 * 0,4 * 1,6 + (100 - (100 * 0,4)) = 40 * 1,6 + 60 = 64 + 60.$

*Example with a FWCI **under** the world average (i.e. under 1):*

In this case, the department will lose publication points and receive 96 publication points
 $100 * 0,4 * 0,9 + (100 - (100 * 0,4)) = 40 * 0,9 + 60 = 36 + 60.$

Open Science Indicators (part B)

Collaboration, Visibility and Openness

- Accounts for **new international agendas** (ARRA og DORA)
- Statistics to use in the annual **department performance agreements**
- **Narrative descriptions** of the focus areas. Qualified arguments for strategic selection

Strategic Performance Agreements: Align with the University's overall strategy (part B)

Aalborg University is a mission driven university

One year performance agreements between department and faculty level

The new research indicator fits within this framework and contributes to strategic decisions on research, publishing, and dissemination

Both long and short-term goals to accommodate for delays in changing strategies within publishing

Collaboration - Data

	Data	Coverage	Source + Degree of System Support	Implementation	Cost
External collaboration	Publications, activities and projects	100% for publications Varying for activities and projects	Pure (100%)	Existing practice (publications) New practice (activities and projects); NB: membership registration standard since 2021	VBN team: existing task
Internal collaboration	Publications and projects	100% for publications Varying for projects	Pure (100%)	Existing practice (publications)	VBN team: existing task Researchers: project registration - new task
Students	Publications	Varying to good	Pure (100%)	Existing practice at some departments	VBN team: existing/new task
Tecnical and administrative staff	Publications	100% - if they are at the author list	Pure (100%)	Existing practice at some departments	VBN team: existing/new task
Innovation projects*	Projects	Varying to good	Pure (100%)	Existing practice at some departments	VBN team: existing/new task
Referral and guidance in connection with the AAU Startup Program and project-oriented courses in your own startup	Referral and guidance in connection	100%	AAU Innovation CRM-system (100%)	Existing practice	AAU Innovation: existing task

*to be defined

Visibility - Data

	Data	Coverage	Source + Degree of System Support	Implementation	Cost
Media coverage	Press cuttings	100%	Pure (100%) and Infomedia (cf. source list)	Existing practice	VBN team: existing task
Online attention	Publication's PlumX data	Varying as to the tradition for use of SoMe	Pure (100%)	Existing practice	VBN team: existing task
Societal impact	Impact registrations (include minimum # relations)	Varying use	Pure (100%) and Infomedia (cf. source list)	New practice	VBN team: new task Researchers: approval and enrichment of the registration
Reporting of research results with commercial potential	Reports cf. "Lov om Opfindelser"	100%	AAU Innovation CRM-system and Initium (100%)	Existing practice	AAU Innovation (existing practice)
Commercialization, startups and spin-outs/CVR registrations	License, sales and option agreements and company formation	100% if AAU Innovation has been involved. Varies according to the departments' registration of side job agreements	AAU Innovation CRM-system and Initium (100%)	Existing practice	AAU Innovation (existing practice) AAU Departments (existing practice)
Open Entrepreneurship	Registration, activities held, participation and projects	100% if AAU Innovation has been involved. Varies depending on the departments' registration	AAU Innovation CRM-system (100%)	Existing practice	AAU Innovation (existing practice) AAU Departments (probably existing practice)

Openness - Data

	Data	Coverage	Source + Degree of System Support	Implementation	Cost
Open Access	Publications and dataset	Varying as to possibilities for green resp. golden OA	Pure (80%-100% cf. indicator), Data Monitor (cf. source list)	Existing practice	VBN team: existing task Researchers: existing task (accepted manuscript)
Membership in external fora	Activities - membership	Varying use	Pure (100%)	Existing/new practice NB: membership registration standard since 2021	VBN team: existing/new task Researchers: implementation of standard on different levels
Active profile on vbn.aau.dk	Pure profiles	Varying use	Pure (100%)	Existing/new practice	VBN team: existing/new task Researchers: use of this feature on different levels
Innovation-promoting events*	Participation in innovation events	Varying use	Pure (100%)	Existing practice	VBN team: new task Researchers: new task

*to be defined

A dynamic indicator

- The indicator is constructed with the possibility to adjust the distribution between part A and part B (70/30)
- At the same time, the content in part B can be adjusted to match changes to AAU's strategy and new agendas in the surrounding society.

Organizational set-up and division of responsibilities

- SRFI: Responsibility for the AAU Research Indicator
- Dean's Office: Approval of performance agreements
- Departments: Preparation of performance agreements
- Finance and accounts department: Calculation and distribution of funds
- The research analysis team:
 - Support for performance agreements statistics
 - Teaching and instruction in relation to publishing strategy
 - Calculation of points
 - Guidance regarding performance agreements based on new initiatives at national and European level
 - Responsible for continued monitoring of the indicator and possible development of the indicator

AAU Research and Innovation Indicator

What is it?

Open Science inspired – quantitative and qualitative

A range of metrics – statistics

Setting a direction for AAU and departments

Raising single researchers' awareness of the international OS agenda + OS skillset

What is it *not*?

ONE number
(e.g., BFI sum or H-index)

Usable for benchmark between departments (part B)

Usable for benchmark between single researchers

How to use the AAU Indicator at individual and group level

- The AAU indicator is designed to be used at department level in terms of allocation of funding.
- However, it is possible for research groups and researchers to work with both part A and part B to enhance the bibliometric and the open science elements of the indicator.

Conclusions

- An indicator with two parts ensures the possibility to measure using known indicators and metrics such as citations and number of publications and, at the same time, add new valuable qualitative focus areas
- The indicator is designed for use at department level
- The indicator is used as a tool for recourse allocation as well as strategic considerations
- The points from the indicator are aggregated to faculty and university level in an annual report
- The indicator is internationally recognizable by using traditional bibliometric indicators as well as by including new trends and demands for research assessment in an Open Science perspective.

Danish CoARA Chapter - Momentum

December 3-4, 2025

Copenhagen

<https://cerra.aau.dk>

EU HIGH-LEVEL CONFERENCE ON REFORMING RE- SEARCH ASSESS- MENT

As part of Denmark's Presidency of the Council of the European Union, Aalborg University together with international partners is hosting a conference on reforming research assessment on December 3-4, 2025 at Tivoli Hotel & Congress Center in Copenhagen. The conference is supported by the European Commission.

Pedersen, D. B., Bjerg Bennike, K., & Melchiorsen, P. M. (2026). From Principle to Practice in Reforming Research Assessment: Policy Brief. Aalborg Universitet.
<https://doi.org/10.54337/aau.policybrief.euprra>

Danske underskrivere af ARRA

Copenhagen Business
School

[Website](#)

University College Absalon

[Website](#)

Roskilde University

[Website](#)

VELUX FONDEN

[Website](#)

Villum Foundation

[Website](#)

Technical University of
Denmark

[Website](#)

IT University of Copenhagen

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Aalborg University

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Aarhus Universitet

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Independent Research Fund
Denmark

[Website](#)

The Danish National
Research Foundation

[Website](#)

University of Copenhagen

[Website](#)

University of Southern
Denmark

[Website](#)

Lundbeck Foundation

[Website](#)

Det Danske National Chapter

The mission of the Danish National Chapter is to provide a national platform for CoARA in Denmark to engage key stakeholders, facilitate mutual exchange, share best practices, and to pave the way for developments in research assessment that both recognises the diversity of research activities, outputs, and practices, but also further drive quality in research.

Main objectives include:

- Exchange of experiences and best practice procedures among institutions and funders
- Provide insight into research assessment procedures and practices among institutions
- Inspire and develop new ideas based on national as well as international initiatives
- Align research assessment procedures across institutions when relevant

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/coara-danish-national-chapter/>

<https://www.coara.org/national-chapters/coara-national-chapter-denmark/>

CoARA og AAU

- ▶ Aalborg Universitet underskrev ARRA i marts 2023 og blev samtidig medlem af CoARA.
- ▶ Dette indebærer, at vi har udarbejdet en action plan for hvordan vi vil arbejde med CoARA principperne på AAU.
- ▶ VBN-teamet er AAU's CoARA sekretariat og kontakt til det nationale chapter og det internationale CoARA sekretariatet
- ▶ Hvis I har forslag til emner/initiativer er I meget velkomne til at række ud og så kan vi hjælpe med at formidle og koordinere
- ▶ CoARA har et fokus på at reformere rekruttering og meriteringsstrukturer ift. ansættelser og bedømmelser af forskere. Her spiller HR og rekrutteringsmateriale en stor rolle, samt bedømmelseskriterier fx for lektorer.

Further Reading

- Main report on the AAU Research Indicator:
<https://vbn.aau.dk/en/publications/the-aau-research-indicator-for-the-advancement-of-scientific-publ>
- Guide to the AAU Research Indicator:
<https://vbn.aau.dk/en/publications/guide-aau-forskningsindikator-guide-to-aau-research-indikator>
- Data and Guide to the strategic performance agreements in AAU Research Indicator (part B):
<https://vbn.aau.dk/en/publications/aauforskningsindikator-del-b-data-katalog-og-guide-til-institut->
- [Quick Guide for AAU Research Indicator](#)